

A Spatial–Descriptive Paradigm of Non-Food Delivery-Based Enterprises: An Emphasis on Challenges and Opportunities

Crugie Boy A. Vitobina¹, Shane M. Dumagat², Cyrene Joy P. Santillan³, Bryan S. Maglaque⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Research and Extension Unit

Cavite State University – CCAT Campus Rosario, Cavite, Philippines

* *crugieboy.vitobina@cvsu.edu.ph*

Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic caused so many challenges that business owners were forced to stretch their strategies to survive and sustain their operations. Hence, the researchers aimed to determine and analyze the challenges and opportunities of non-food delivery-based enterprises amidst the pandemic. The researchers purposively selected 70 non-food delivery-based enterprises. A spatial-descriptive design was used to process and interpret the study. Considerably, the findings of the study revealed that non-food delivery-based enterprises in the municipality of Tanza, Cavite, were mostly under sole proprietorship, with limited staff, a business capitalization range below Php 3,000,000, and newly opened businesses. The study identified key challenges were cash borrowing, resource management, maintaining a consistent customer experience, new marketing trends, and curfew hours. On the other hand, selling more products or services, improving customer feedback, investing in developing business opportunities, and using new technology to increase efficiency are key opportunities. The researchers recommend strengthening marketing strategies that focus on enabling mechanisms for financial sustainability, customer satisfaction, and flexibility in the pandemic-led market environment.

Keywords: *challenges, COVID-19 pandemic, delivery enterprises, descriptive research, opportunities*

1. Introduction

Inside a society, business plays a significant role. It is an innovative and competitive endeavor that leads to the shaping of our culture continuously. The business increases people's quality of life and raises their standard of living by meeting needs and desires they cannot meet for themselves, which is true locally; and internationally (Mendoza & Tadeo, 2022). The primary purpose of establishing a business is to provide products and services to people to earn profit. Enterprises have an important role in society; aside from creating and providing products and services to clients, they also contribute to the economy by giving employment that can help accelerate economic development. Moreover, business enterprises become crucial to the market since they can grow the nation's economy (Mohamed, 2020). Business operations have become more convenient due to the increase in digital technology. They can be more flexible in communication and promotion, which can increase their sales and improve brand awareness. Delivery transactions nowadays can be done through a door-to-door transaction. Additionally, technology helps business enterprises to lower their costs, unlike before they needed to spend a lot to promote their products and service offer (Dwivedi et al., 2021).

Consequently, certain socio-economic changes affect a business's operation, including globalization, continuous innovation, digital pressure, and competitive pressure (Mendoza et al., 2023). Businesses must have explosive adoption of technologies and tools that support their internal and external processes (Regragui, 2020) and (Tadeo & Mojica, 2022). However, business enterprises can experience different challenges environmentally, like the COVID-19 pandemic.

This pandemic is one of the biggest challenges businesses face. It reduces sales, increases costs and labor, affects many economic and business activities worldwide (Romo et al., 2020), and leads to shutdowns (Dagpin et al., 2022).

Furthermore, business enterprises can still operate. It has become more convenient since delivery services can send the items directly to clients in both food and non-food enterprises. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, business enterprise challenges have increased in terms of their operations, most especially in non-food enterprises.

The result of this research provided benefits to those marketers willing to take their businesses into a delivery-based one since this would give them an awareness of the possible challenges they may encounter in this field. Furthermore, it offers ideas and opportunities to overcome such challenges in operating a delivery-based enterprise.

In general, the purpose of this research was to identify the challenges and opportunities of non-food delivery-based businesses in Tanza, Cavite, in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic. The specific objective of the research was to identify the respondents' profile in terms of ownership type, number of employees, capitalization range, and length of operation. The challenges in operation, marketing, management/leadership, and quarantine compliance were also identified. Significant opportunities for respondents in terms of business expansion, sales, and technology adoption in the face of the pandemic were identified. Finally, potential solutions to non-food delivery-based challenges were presented.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Enterprises during the COVID-19 pandemic

Some businesses have a long and storied history and have been through previous crises. They choose firms based on the contacts of the research team, and they cover all of Macao's major industries, including hospitality, wholesale and retail, real estate, private education, skilled services, and food. In order to avoid traceability, they use alphabets to classify the participating businesses (Yin, 2011, as cited in Alves et al., 2020). The challenge of crisis resolution has been reinterpreted as a normal stage (Välikangas and Lewin, 2020, as cited in Alves et al., 2020), a novel concept that warrants further investigation and debate. However, some of the tactics used in previous crises could still be useful for small businesses; however, the COVID-19 pandemic's novelty necessitates them to expand stakeholder participation and develop new learning. Fabeil et al. (2020) mentioned that many countries have imposed travel restrictions and movement controls because of the COVID-19 pandemic. The small business sector in Malaysia is one of the most impacted by the movement's control order. Microbusinesses experienced a greater impact than their larger counterparts. Due to the shutdown of many supporting sectors, such as retail and transportation, entrepreneurs are experiencing company cancellation or closure and reduced profits. The impact-reduction techniques entrepreneurs use in this study are like (Cook, 2015, as cited in Fabeil et al. 2020) crisis phases, which include reacting, resuming, healing, and restoring. According to the entrepreneurs interviewed, the post-crisis period may only last twelve months after the crisis has ended, which is the restoring phase. Fabeil et al. (2020) stated that entrepreneurs gained more expertise, skills, and capital during this stage to help them recover from the crisis. Such expertise has become the foundation for company recovery plans, such as reorganizing a business model or philosophy, revising a business strategy, reviewing consumer segments, and learning how to conduct business in the new standard. Due to its abrupt risks, the COVID-19 crisis can be considered a tough situation for microenterprises. Entrepreneurs seemed to demonstrate

their ability to stay in business by implementing a variety of business continuity and recovery strategies, especially in product distribution and marketing. The businesses help people out of poverty, provide employment opportunities, and innovative settings for entrepreneurs to create new goods and services (Mendoza et al., 2023).

As the surge in delivery services keeps the business afloat, even if they are closed, there are still some challenges that delivery businesses face. Digital platforms allow the customers' shopping experience to include reviews, comparing the products, and the ability to pay using electronic transactions by checking out their parcels (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2020). According to Peñarubia (2020), people tend to copy and prepare their food at home but still crave the different dishes from their favorite restaurants. Delivery services are the only option that becomes the opportunity for the restaurants to take and explore the business that they didn't have tried before. As customers fear the transmission of the virus, maintaining good hygiene practices when accepting deliveries is highly recommended. Food loss will never be an issue because it creates a positive impact by delivering it in portions. But still, there is no guarantee that food deliveries are free from food waste, just like mishandling and delay resulting in rejections. Moreover, prank calls or bogus buyers can also result in food waste. It also depends on the consumer behavior, assessing the flavor and taste, proper portion size, and being a responsible user by recognizing the legitimate app or phone calls that may vary to decrease the food waste or loss.

2.2 Delivery-based enterprises during the pandemic

COVID-19 outbreak brought advantages to the online food delivery business. Nonetheless, online food delivery is still unsafe for consumers and restaurant critics. The purpose of the study is to stock and consider the broader impacts of food delivery and the meaning of the involvement of stakeholders. Online food delivery brings the first interdisciplinary review and academic research to the broad areas impacted. Second, these impacts pose opportunities and challenges that have been discussed. Third, maximization of positivity and reducing disadvantages gives opportunities for action by all stakeholders, together with food delivery practitioners, politicians, consumers, and academics are emphasized. The researcher also added that the future of online food delivery is exciting, continuous reflection on what's happening and seeking the things that will be done better, ensuring the sector develops in a maintainable manner with the help of the involved stakeholder's interest (Li et al., 2020). According to Hussey (2020), for the adaptation of the new normal, third-party delivery services arises the restaurants as the consumer follows the social distancing rule to avoid the virus. Before the pandemic, restaurants only allowed a single third party for their delivery services, but due to the current status of our environment, it has tripled. Delivery services help mitigate the costs in this time of disruption and ease when COVID-19 is no longer a threat in normal conditions for restaurants. In this time of uncertainty, the rate of adaptation to the new technologies, regulations, and many ways of working, makes the thousands of operators offer uninterrupted service.

2.3 Challenges of delivery-based enterprises

According to Velita (2022), non-food MSMEs suffered losses due to the pandemic, while other MSMEs migrated to the food industry to meet their monthly obligations. Food delivery and courier services have increased to deliver essential and non-essential commodities to consumers. Furthermore, (Ratnasingam et al., 2020) discussed how most SMEs (Small and Medium

Enterprises) were operating at or below capacity, putting a significant financial strain on their business viability. During the crisis, the two main concerns of SMEs were financial management and supply chain disruptions. Furthermore, over 83% of businesses needed more preparation and a plan for dealing with such a situation. The findings of the study by Bolton et al. (2018) identified eight dualities or challenges associated with integrating digital, bodily, and social geographical areas that challenge businesses to create advanced client stories in both enterprise-to-business and enterprise-to-patron markets. However, according to Hoekstra and Leeflang (2020), many companies need a greater understanding of efficiency. They were primarily concerned with short-term cost reductions at the micro level, paying little or no attention to the time, energy, and productive resources expended in their operational processes. According to (Sumagaysay, 2020), to adapt to the new standard, third-party delivery services emerge and become a new marketing trend for restaurants that closed due to the pandemic but still want to continue serving and delivering customer orders. The difficulties were directly related to the latest activities they were expected to perform at work and the decreased social connection, emphasizing the need for organizational support to reduce the stressful working conditions for employees and managers (Kirchner et al., 2021).

2.4 Opportunities for delivery-based enterprises

According to Park and Chung (2019), international business expansion provides opportunities for the company's growth, competitiveness, and admission to new product ideas. Furthermore, Lou (2021) stated that e-business represented a new revolution in how businesses could gain an advantage over their competitors and increase total revenue and productivity. Furthermore, the researcher proposed several actions that could increase customer trust, such as improving privacy and security policies, rewarding customers based on their monthly purchases or the amount they spend, and providing discounts or other incentives for purchasing large quantities of their products. The findings of the Sumagaysay (2020) study revealed that the pandemic boosts the industry in these delivery apps like Uber Eats, Postmates, and Grub as the combined revenue from April to September reached \$5.5 billion, more than doubling the \$2.5 billion from the same period last year. Uber Eats' bookings increased by 135% year over year, increasing their revenue to \$1.4 billion or 125%, putting them in competition with Amazon Inc. and Walmart Inc. Fairlie and Fossen's (2021) study, on the other hand, contradicted the study's findings that sales losses in the deal to mandated lockdowns, such as hotels, were highest (91%). Despite this, specific industries experienced significant growth, such as online sales, which increased by 18% as consumers moved away from in-store purchases. According to Haseeb et al. (2019), industry 4.0 is the key to long-term business performance growth among SMEs. Furthermore, integrating innovative financing and technological adaptation, according to Pu et al. (2021), promotes the sustainability of SMEs. They also suggested that policy development and implementation begin, focusing on efficient online financial services, closing corporate deals, and utilizing IT improvements in operations.

2.5 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Study paradigm of challenges and opportunities of non-food delivery-based enterprises

Figure 1. shows the process of conducting the research. The researchers used a spatial-descriptive design to determine the profile, opportunities, and challenges of the non-food delivery-based enterprise. Additionally, primary data and a review of related literature are utilized to gather information needed in the study. Furthermore, this research identifies the challenges and opportunities through filtering, sequence, and compressing to provide a possible strategy for the non-food delivery-based enterprises in Tanza, Cavite.

3. Methodology

3.1 Design and Methods

The researchers used a spatial-descriptive research design to describe, explain and interpret the present point of view of the target participants, as well as to understand the challenges and opportunities of non-food delivery-based enterprises during the COVID-19 pandemic. Considerably, purposive sampling was used to determine the participants based on who was appropriate for the study through a scanning and screening approach. Non-food delivery-based enterprises in Tanza, Cavite, served as participants in the study. The researchers used primary and secondary data collected through online survey questionnaires. The secondary data was gathered through reviews of relevant literature and online studies using academic sources. Questionnaires were used to gather data on the challenges and opportunities of non-food delivery-based enterprises. Moreover, the survey questionnaire was subjected to reliability and validity tests and had a Cronbach alpha of 0.72, providing a valid coefficient value. In order to interpret the data effectively, the researchers employed frequency count, percentage, and mean analysis as statistical tools.

3.2 Ethical Consideration

The researchers obtained informed consent from the respondents and maintained the respondents' prior anonymity and privacy. Also, anonymity was maintained, ensuring no physical, emotional, or social harm was caused.

4. Result and Discussion

Table 1 presents the business profile of non-food delivery-based enterprises in Tanza, Cavite. It showcases that most non-food delivery-based were sole proprietorships, with 72.86 responses. Considerably, 91.40 percent of total responses belong to 1 to 9 number of staffs. Moreover, most of the non-food delivery based in Tanza, Cavite, has below Php 3,000,000 as business capitalization range with 74.30 percent of the total responses. Furthermore, the study depicts that 75.70 percent of the participants belong to 0 to 5 years as their length of operations.

Table 1. Business profile of non-food delivery-based enterprises

Categories		Frequency	Percentage
Type of Ownership	Sole Proprietorship	51	72.86
	Partnership	10	14.29
	Corporation	8	11.43
	Cooperative	1	1.43
Number of staff	1 to 9	64	91.40
	10 to 49	5	7.10
	50 to 249	1	1.40
Business Capitalization Range	Below Php 3,000,000	52	74.30
	Php 3,000,001 to Php 15,000,000	7	10.00
	Php 15,000,001 to Php 100,000,000	6	8.60
	Php 100,000,001 and above	5	7.10
Length of operations	0 to 5 years	52	75.70
	6 to 10 years	7	10.00
	11 to 20 years	5	7.10
	21 years and above	5	7.10

Table 2 shows the challenges encountered by the non-food delivery-based enterprises in Tanza, Cavite, in terms of operation. It reveals that 22.80% of the participants mentioned that they have challenges with cash, borrowing, and resource management, and the least was the environmental sustainability of four percent or six among the 149 multiple responses of participants. This confirmed that most of the SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) were operating below their capacity, which was a huge financial strain on their business viability. The two major concerns of the SMEs during this crisis were financial management and supply chain disruptions, as studied (Ratnasingam et al., 2020). This was also supported by Velita (2022) study, that non-food MSMEs faced losses due to the pandemic, while other MSMEs migrated to the food industry to meet their monthly responsibilities. There was an increase in food delivery and courier services to transfer essential and non-essential commodities to consumers. According to the study by Shafi et al. (2020), the majority of the participating firms were negatively impacted and were dealing with a variety of problems, including financial difficulties, supply chain disruptions, a drop

in demand, a decline in sales, and a loss of profit, among others. In addition, over 83% of businesses lacked preparation and a plan for handling such a circumstance.

Table 2. Challenges of non-food delivery-based enterprises in terms of operation

Category	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Cash, Borrowing, and Resource Management	34	22.80	1
Supply Shortage	31	20.80	2
Increased Selection and Competition	23	15.40	3
Regulation	14	9.40	5
Problem-Solving and Risk Management	10	6.70	7
Shortage of Staff	12	8.10	6
Cost Management	19	12.80	4
Environmental Sustainability	6	4.00	8
Total	149	100.00	

Table 3 showcases the challenges faced by the non-food delivery-based enterprises in Tanza, Cavite, regarding marketing. It depicts that 25.30% of the total responses divulge that they have challenges as to maintaining a consistent customer experience, and one among the 146 multiple responses the participants answered others, specifically the participant mentioned that they experience challenges in the unfamiliar brand product they are trying to sell to their customers. The study (Bolton et al., 2018) confirmed this, identifying eight dualities or demanding situations linked with integrating digital, bodily, and social geographical regions that challenge the businesses to create advanced client stories in each commercial enterprise-to-commercial enterprise and commercial enterprise-to-patron markets. Hoekstra and Leeftang (2020) found that many businesses had a limited understanding of what efficiency entailed. They were primarily concerned with short-term cost reductions at the micro level, with little or no regard for the time, energy, and productive resources used in their operational processes. Some companies have taken this limited approach to an extreme, leading to widespread outsourcing rather than in-house manufacturing, low stock levels, high reliance on foreign manufacturers, and low prices.

Table 3. Challenges of non-food delivery-based enterprises in terms of marketing

Category	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Sharpening Effectiveness	22	15.10	2
Inspiring others	21	14.40	3
Developing Employees	10	6.80	6
Leading a team	9	6.20	7
Guiding Change	9	6.20	7
Keeping up with platform changes	19	13.00	4
Maintaining a Consistent Customer Experience	37	25.30	1
Tracking performance metrics accurately	18	12.30	5
Others	1	0.70	8
Total	146	100.00	

Table 4 reveals the challenges faced by the non-food delivery-based enterprises in Tanza, Cavite, regarding management/leadership. It implies that 29.40% of the participants stated they

have challenges in the new marketing trend, and 1.70% or two among the 119 multiple responses of the participants answered others, specifically, the participants mentioned that they have no staff. The other one responded that they were not allowed to give flyers in promoting the business since the pandemic started. It was clearly stated that delivery-based enterprises were challenged in terms of management. This was similar to the study (Sumagaysay, 2020), which revealed that for the adaptation of the new normal, third-party delivery services arise and become a new marketing trend for restaurants that are closed due to the pandemic and still want to continue serving and delivering the orders of the customers. Both delivery apps like Instacart and Uber declare losses because of unpredictable outcomes of demand and new offerings turning into profit. According to the findings, the challenges were directly related to the new activities they were expected to perform at work and reduced social connection. This emphasizes the need for organizational support to lessen the stressful employment conditions for employees and managers (Kirchner et al., 2021).

Table 4. Challenges of non-food delivery-based enterprises in terms of management/leadership

Category	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Inexperience or Understaffed	18	15.10	3
New Marketing Trend	35	29.40	1
Lack of Communication	13	10.00	5
Marketing Logistics	21	17.60	2
Resolving Conflict	14	11.80	4
Retaining Employees	10	8.40	6
Firing of staff	6	5.00	7
others	2	1.70	8
Total	119	100.00	

Table 5 displays the challenges faced by the non-food delivery-based enterprises in Tanza, Cavite, regarding quarantine compliance. It showcases that 21.20% of the participants mentioned that they have challenges in the implementation of curfew hours by the local government, and the least which was the vaccination documents and isolation of 6.50% or 14 among the 217 multiple responses of the participants. The study (Al-Khalaifah et al., 2020) confirmed that the curfew measured the cause of a disruption to the distribution chain by the restriction movement of the government, which caused restaurants and selling retail completely close. As a result, it caused a negative impact on the company and marketing sector to decline in their sales. It was also discussed in the study (Atienza & Tabuena, 2021) that business owners were taking care to become friendly and open to the potential clients and consumers of their products. The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the Philippines' economic sector, and these issues must be handled sooner rather than later. Iriwan (2020) mentioned that in the new normal time, product hygiene and environmental sanitation were more important determinants of SMEs' existence than computer technology was for improving consumer trust and income.

Table 5. Challenges of non-food delivery-based enterprises in terms of quarantine compliance

Category	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage
Curfew	46	21.20	1
Vaccination Documents	14	6.50	7
Sanitizing the Working Area	15	6.90	6
Face Mask	29	13.40	4
Face Shield	21	9.70	5
Social Distancing	32	14.70	3
Isolation	14	6.50	7
Lockdown	45	20.70	2
others	1	.50	9
Total	217	100.00	

Table 6 presents the opportunities for non-food delivery-based enterprises in Tanza, Cavite, in terms of business expansion. It shows that 16.70% of the participants stated that they have a target new customer market, and the least was offering franchise ownership to other entrepreneurs with 4.60% of total responses. This was supported by the study (Park & Chung, 2019) that international business expansion allows the company to increase, enables growth competitiveness, and admission to new product ideas. The study by Lou (2021) mentioned that e-business represented a fresh revolution in how businesses could get an edge over their competitors and expand total revenue and productivity. Additionally, the researcher proposed a variety of actions that could be taken to increase customer trust, including enhancing privacy and safety policies, rewarding customers based on their monthly purchases or the amount they spend, and providing discounts or other incentives for buying large quantities of their products.

Table 6. Opportunities for non-food delivery-based enterprises in terms of business expansion

Category	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Offering franchise ownership to other entrepreneurs	10	4.60	7
Products and/or services are increasingly in demand	35	16.20	3
Profits have been strong for several years	29	13.40	4
Costs are under control consistently	23	10.60	5
Availability of resources (financial, personnel, materials)	29	13.40	4
Target new customer markets	36	16.70	2
Expand into new territories	15	6.90	6
Sell more products or services to existing customers	38	17.60	1
Others	1	.50	8
Total	216	100.00	

Table 7 reveals the opportunities of non-food delivery-based enterprises in Tanza, Cavite, in terms of sales. Noticeably, 18.10% of the total responses divulged that enterprises had grown the existing accounts, and the least was the accountable management, with 4.60% of total responses. This was confirmed (Sumagaysay, 2020) that the pandemic gives a boost to the industry in these delivery apps like Uber Eats, Postmates, and Grub as the combined revenue from April and September reached \$5.5 billion compared to the same period last year that more than doubled

of \$2.5 billion. Uber Eats' booking increased by 135% year over year, surging their revenue to \$1.4 billion or 125%, which makes them, together with Door dash compete with Amazon Inc. and Walmart Inc. However, the study of Fairlie and Fossen (2021) contradicted the findings of a study that sales losses in deals to mandated lockdowns, such as hotels, were highest (91%). Nonetheless, certain industries saw significant growth, such as online sales, which increased by 18% as consumers shifted away from in-store purchases.

Table 7. Opportunities for non-food delivery-based enterprises in terms of sales

Category	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Invest in other opportunities to develop business	34	17.60	2
Invest in effective sales-skills training	25	13.00	3
Grow the existing accounts	35	18.10	1
Develop sales managers	12	6.20	5
Build goal and action plans	25	13.00	3
Accountable Management	9	4.70	6
Accurate forecasting	19	9.80	4
Better Implementation of Customer Feedback	34	17.60	2
Total	193	100.00	

Table 8 presents the opportunities for non-food delivery-based enterprises in Tanza, Cavite, in terms of technology adaptation. Considerably, 21.30 percent of the total respondents stated that new technology increases efficiency. The remote work challenges and decreased training and support costs were the least, with 5.20 percent of total responses. This was confirmed by the study (Haseeb et al., 2019) that Industry 4.0 was the key to sustainable business performance growth among SMEs. Industry 4.0 elements such as big data, the Internet of things, and smart factories positively encourage the application of information technology (IT) that contributes to the sustainability of business performance. Moreover, the study of Pu et al. (2021) showed that integrating innovative financing and technological adaptation favorably promotes the sustainability of SMEs.

Table 8. Opportunities for non-food delivery-based enterprises in terms of technology adaptation

Category	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
New Technology Increases Efficiency	45	21.30	1
Lower Current Workload	39	18.50	2
Remote Work Challenges	11	5.20	7
Technology Positions for Future Growth	33	15.60	3
Technology Differentiates	17	8.10	6
Increased Productivity	28	13.30	4
Decrease training and support costs	11	5.20	7
Improved user onboarding	27	12.80	5
Total	211	100.00	

5. Conclusion

After the collected data presented in this study, the researchers found out that the non-food delivery-based enterprises in Tanza, Cavite, were identified to be mostly sole proprietorship enterprises with limited staff. It was also determined that these delivery-based enterprises were starting with a business capital range of below Php 3,000,000, most of which were newly open.

The participants were assessed by conducting online survey questionnaires via Google Forms and it was concluded that in terms of operation, most of the non-food delivery-based enterprises had a challenge in cash, borrowing, and resource management. It also revealed that non-food delivery-based enterprises had a challenge in maintaining a consistent customer experience when it came to their marketing. Moreover, in terms of management/leadership, most of the non-food delivery-based enterprises had a challenge with new marketing trends. When it comes to quarantine compliance, it showed that most of the non-food delivery-based enterprises had a challenge with imposed curfew hours by the local government.

Furthermore, the study concluded that the non-food delivery-based enterprises in Tanza, Cavite, had an opportunity amidst the pandemic. It revealed that in terms of business expansion, most of the non-food delivery-based enterprises target new customer markets even though the government imposes protocols. In terms of sales, most of the non-food delivery-based enterprises were growing their existing accounts despite the hindrance in operating the enterprise. Lastly, most of the non-food delivery-based enterprises in Tanza, Cavite, were engaging in the new trend of technology to maximize their business operation.

6. Recommendation

This understanding comes to various conclusions and analyses as the data presented were analyzed. Hereby, the researchers have the following recommendation. Since this study revealed that cash, borrowing, and resource management is a challenges addressed in terms of operation, the researchers recommend proper monitoring where enterprises prepare a monthly business budget to track the money coming in and out. This may help the business to know if they are suffering from loss and give a solution. Identify and refine the resource implications of the review about the current and previous performance and build a budget. Then, define the new financial year's profit, loss, and balance sheet targets. Conclude and review the plan regularly and accept online payment to secure the payment. It might include an option for a G-cash or Pay-pal payment check out on-site and payment through cash on delivery to avoid the pending payment.

The study showed that in terms of maintaining a consistent customer experience. The researchers recommend a customer-centered design where staff is accommodating of inquiries at all times, providing a timely and personalized response, does not have an automatic response set up when it comes to inquiries, and always treats them with respect to create a real relationship or connection, exceeding the customer experience to give a good impact by providing quality services and after-sales service and provide excellent customer service, analyze patterns and trends associated with their customer segments also create a captivating digital experience for prospects and customers.

As to management/leadership, they have challenges with new marketing trends. The researchers recommend managing the changes and implementing them by making strategies, conducting research about the current trends and analyzing them, choosing which among trends is appropriate to the business as well as to the budget and implementing it then, check whether the chosen marketing trend gives to benefit the business, ensuring that the information is always up to date with new social media trends, check through social media which is a new and popular marketing trend among customers and Carefully examine the new trend and make a judgment about it and sell it to the current customers to generate income. Also, the researchers found that in terms

of quarantine compliance, they have challenges with curfew hours implemented by the local government. The researchers recommend asking permission from the local government to operate beyond the given business hours. Since these enterprises were operating delivery-based, they do not have physical contact and staff evaluation and assessment, scan the information about your employees, separate those employees who can work beyond the curfew, finalize the plan, and regularly monitor for effectiveness. These recommendations were applicable to non-food delivery-based enterprises. Lastly, the authors recommend that the future researcher focuses on the variables not undertaken by the study as to the opportunities of delivery-based enterprises to further understand and propose strategies for strengthening the non-food delivery-based enterprises.

7. Acknowledgement

The researchers would like to thank the Cavite State University - CCAT Campus Research and Extension Unit for making this study possible. They also value the presence of their loved ones and friends as a source of motivation to pursue and complete this endeavor. Most notably, Almighty God's divine guidance and wisdom.

References

- Al-Khalaifah, H., Al-Nasser, A., Abdulmalek, N., Al-Mansour, H., Ahmed, A., & Ragheb, G. (2020). Impact of SARS-Con-V2 on the poultry industry in Kuwait: A case study. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 7, 577178. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2020.577178>
- Alves, J.C., Lok, T.C., Luo, Y. et al. Crisis challenges of small firms in Macao during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Frontiers of Business Research in China*. 14(26). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s11782-020-00094-2>
- Atienza, M. A., & Tabuena, A. C. (2021). The Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Managerial Accounting and Its Adjustments in Financial Markets. *International Journal of Business, Technology and Organizational Behavior*. 1(4), 287–296. <https://doi.org/10.52218/ijbtob.v1i4.109>
- Bolton, R.N., McColl-Kennedy, J.R., Cheung, L., Gallan, A., Orsingher, C., Witell, L. & Zaki, M. (2018). Customer experience challenges: bringing together digital, physical, and social realms. *Journal of Service Management*. 29 (5), 776 808. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOSM-04-2018-0113>
- Dagpin, J.C., Escaño, A.R., Mendoza, X.L.D., Vertuso, J.C., (2022). Microenterprises shutdown amidst COVID-19 pandemic: A focus on determinants and exit strategies, *Asia Pacific Journal of Academic Research in Business Administration*, (8)1, 22-28. <https://research.lpubatangas.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/3-APJARBA-2022-28.pdf>
- Dayton, D. (2019). What Is a Business Enterprise? Retrieved from. <https://bizfluent.com/about-6721330-business-enterprise-.html>
- Dwivedi, Y. K., Ismagilova, E., Hughes, D. L., Carlson, J., Filieri, R., Jacobson, J., ... & Wang, Y. (2021). Setting the future of digital and social media marketing research: Perspectives and

- research propositions. *International Journal of Information Management*, 59, 102–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2020.102168>
- Fabeil, N., Pazim, K., Langgat, J. (2020). The impact of covid-19 pandemic crisis on micro-enterprises: entrepreneurs' perspective on business continuity and recovery strategy. *Journal of Economics and Business*. 3(2), 837-844. DOI: 10.31014/aior.1992.03.02.241
- Fairlie, R., Fossen, F.M. (2022). The early impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on business sales. *Small Business Economic*. 58,. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-021-00479-4>
- Haseeb, Muhammad, Hussain, H. I., Ślusarczyk, B. & Jermsittiparsert, K. (2019). Industry 4.0: A solution towards technology challenges of sustainable business performance. *Social Sciences*. 8(5), 154. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci8050154>
- Hoekstra, J.C., & Leeflang, P.S.H. (2020). Marketing in the era of COVID-19. *Italian Journal of Marketing*. 249–260. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43039-020-00016-3>
- Hussey, A. (2020). Food Delivery in Demand During COVID-19. *Kerry*. <https://www.kerry.com/insights/kerrydigest/2020/food-delivery-in-demand-during-covid-19>
- Irawan, A. (2020). Challenges and opportunities for small and medium enterprises in eastern Indonesia in facing the COVID-19 pandemic and the new normal era. *The International Journal of Applied Business*, 4(2), 79–89. <https://garuda.kemdikbud.go.id/documents/detail/2035427>
- Kirchner, K., Ipsen, C., & Hansen, J.P. (2021). COVID-19 leadership challenges in knowledge work. *Knowledge Management Research & Practice*. 19(4), 493-500, doi: 10.1080/14778238.2021.1877579
- Li C, Miroso M, Bremer P. (2020). Review of online food delivery platforms and their impacts on sustainability. *Sustainability*, 12(14) 5528. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12145528>
- Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, (2020). Connecting to Business and Consumers during COVID-19: Trade in Parcels. *Tackling Coronavirus (COVID-19): Contributing To A Global Effort*. https://read.oecd-ilibrary.org/view/?ref=135_135520-5u04ajecfy&title=Connecting-Businesses-and-Consumers-During-COVID-19-Trade-in-Parcels
- Luo, C. (2021). Analyzing the impact of social networks and social behavior on electronic business during COVID-19 pandemic. *Information Processing & Management*, 58(5), 102667. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2021.102667>
- Mendoza, X. L., Bruno, L. Y., Maglaque, B. S., & Solis, J. N. (2023). Influence of the factors of business opportunities among micro and small enterprises in selected areas of Cavite. *Asian Journal of Management, Entrepreneurship, and Social Science*, 3(01), 136-155. <https://doi.org/10.98765/ajmesc.v3i01.221>

- Mendoza, X. L. D., Pichay, S. B., & Tadeo, J. B. (2023). Utilization of modified SERVQUAL model in crafting strategies among courier services. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 4(3), 701-712. 10.11594/ijmaber.04.03.03
- Mendoza, X. L. D., & Tadeo, J. B. (2022). Analysis of micro, small, medium enterprises: The cases of Singapore, Malaysia, Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam. *Journal of Management, Economics, and Industrial Organization*, 7(1), 1-15. <http://doi.org/10.31039/jomeino.2023.7.1.1>
- Mohamed, N. (2020). *Top 5 takeaways in the importance of entrepreneurship*. Duke Sanford Center for International Development. <https://dcid.sanford.duke.edu/importance-of-entrepreneurship/>
- Park, H., & Chung, C. C. (2019). The role of subsidiary learning behavior and absorptive capacity in foreign subsidiary expansion. *International Business Review*, 28(4), 685-695. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2019.01.006>
- Peñarubia, O. (2020). *The New Normal in Food Restaurant and Catering Industry-Food Delivery*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nation. <https://www.fao.org/flw-in-fish-value-chains/resources/articles/the-new-normal-in-the-restaurant-and-catering-industryfood-delivery/en/>
- Pu G, Qamruzzaman M, Mehta AM, Naqvi FN, Karim S. (2021). Innovative finance, technological adaptation, and SMEs sustainability: The mediating role of government support during COVID-19 pandemic. *Sustainability*, 13(16):9218. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13169218>
- Ratnasingam, J., Khoo, A., Jegathesan, N., Wei, L. C., Abd Latib, H., Thanasegaran, G., ... & Amir, M. A. (2020). How are small and medium enterprises in Malaysia's furniture industry coping with COVID-19 pandemic? Early evidences from a survey and recommendations for policymakers. *BioResources*, 15(3), 5951-5964. DOI:10.15376/biores.15.3.5951-5964
- Regragui, P. Y. (2020). Determinants of the digital transformation: Exploratory study on the perception of the managers of Moroccan companies. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 22(11), 26-32. DOI: 10.9790/487X-2211072632
- Romo, G.D. A., Sarmiento, J. M. P., Durano, F. L. A., Acuña, T. R., Traje, A. M. & Wahing, G. D. (2020). *Organizational resilience and impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on Philippine businesses*. University of the Philippines Mindanao News <https://www2.upmin.edu.ph/index.php/news-sp-5975/5288-organizational-resilience-and-impacts-of-the-covid-19-pandemic-on-philippine-businesses#>
- Shafi, M., Liu, J., & Ren, W. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on micro, small, and medium-sized Enterprises operating in Pakistan. *Research in Globalization*, 2, 100018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resglo.2020.100018>

Sumagaysay, L. (2020). *The pandemic has more than doubled Food- Delivery apps' business.* MarketWatch. <https://www.marketwatch.com/story/the-pandemic-has-more-than-doubled-americans-use-of-food-delivery-apps-but-that-doesnt-mean-the-companies-are-making-money-11606340169>

Tadeo, J. B., & Mojica, M. A. (2022). The one town, one product program of Cavite Province: A focus on the growth-impeding constraints. *International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management*, 2(4), 1-1. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7563514>